

THE IMPORTANCE OF SPIRITUAL VIRTUES IN THE EDUCATION OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT

In this article, raising youth in the spirit of loyalty to national and humanitarian values, improving their outlook, making them loyal to Independent Uzbekistan will be analyzed.

The development of each country does not depend only on the opportunities and natural resources of the area where it is located. The development of society depends primarily on the level of spiritual maturity of young people. Only patriotic, selfless, hard-working young people with high scientific and moral authority can raise their country to the highest heights of development based on new ideas, new ideas and innovation.

The issue of education of young people, formation of their worldview and all spiritual qualities is becoming extremely important in the critical turning periods of society's development, especially among young people, who are considered the future of our country, and the formation of patriotism, hard work, and national pride among the general population.

As the head of our state noted, today we are moving to the path of innovative development aimed at the radical renewal of all spheres of state and social life.

A new version of the Law "On State Policy Regarding Youth" was adopted in order to raise the work of raising the young generation to be healthy and perfect in all aspects. On this basis, new approaches are being actively introduced to life. Now the International Association of Youth of Uzbekistan will be established. Active communication of young people with their peers abroad in science, culture, entrepreneurship, sports and other fields creates a great opportunity for them to show their potential on a global scale.

Young people do not develop spiritual qualities by themselves. In fact, young people are an important force and a potential resource for the future of every country, causing changes in the society, implementing creative ideas.

Of course, by supporting young people socially, morally and materially, helping them fully realize their rights and obligations, and creating favorable conditions for them to occupy a worthy place in society, they can be turned into a great force that decides the fate and future of the country.

The moral qualities of young people include respect for adults, caring for young people, kindness and humanity, kindness and tolerance, hard work, values, feelings of loyalty to the Motherland and people.

Educating young people in the spirit of loyalty to national and universal human values, expanding their spiritual-aesthetic world view, raising their thinking, protecting young people from all kinds of "mass culture" attacks that have a negative effect on their world view, turning them away from these paths, and becoming true devotees of independent Uzbekistan. The main task of parents, neighborhood, teachers and educators is to work tirelessly with young people.

Spiritual qualities are a set of all positive emotions, spiritual and moral actions of young people that are manifested in daily life activities, such as in the family, neighborhood, street, public transport and places, educational institutions.

So, above, we thought about the essence and some aspects of the main aspects of the spiritual qualities of young people. Now we will think about the relevance of this topic.

For this reason, education of the young generation in our country has risen to the level of state policy. One example of this can be seen in the declaration of 2018 as "the year of support of active entrepreneurship, innovative ideas and technologies" in Uzbekistan.

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 5, 2017 No. 5106 "On supporting the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" of the President of our country and Resolution No. PQ-3138 dated July 18, 2017 "On measures to improve the activities of the Youth Union of Uzbekistan" were approved.

The purpose of approving these decisions is to raise a healthy and well-rounded generation in our country, to realize the creative and intellectual potential of young people, to make the young men and women of our country grow up to be well-rounded individuals who fully meet the requirements of the 21st century. Acceptance of such decisions brought about a big change in the mentality of the youth. The social activity of our youth has increased, the level of political awareness has increased. Most importantly, the entrepreneurial environment in the society was revived.

The state is providing favorable opportunities to young businessmen and creating unprecedented types of production and services in the country, creating many new jobs. So our spiritual young people are being given ample opportunities to implement entrepreneurship and innovative ideas.

Today, the youth of our country are moving to the path of innovative development aimed at the radical renewal of all spheres of society's life. It's not for nothing, of course. Because in today's fast-paced world, who wins? The state that relies on a new idea, a new idea, and innovation will win.

The history, unique customs and traditions, life values of any nation or nation play an important role in the formation and development of qualities and criteria of the spiritual world of a person. As our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev said: "Spirituality is our most effective and powerful weapon." Therefore, it is necessary not to be afraid to tell the truth in front of young people, to avoid fraud, and to clearly state existing difficulties and problems. Qualities and social qualities of young people, such as the level of education, professional skills, moral and spiritual perfection, have a significant impact on the level of development of the entire society.

The President evaluates fundamental changes in the attitude towards the young generation as follows: Issues of working with young people require special attention.

Today, it is very important to increase the place and position of young people in the life of society.

For this reason, the need to study the problems of the young generation and find their solutions based on this is increasing. Another noteworthy aspect of the law on state policy on youth is that it provides for the active and participation of our youth in the international arena along with thorough education, as well as socio-economic protection of minors, orphans, young and large families, talented young people. Issues such as identification and support of those with special bright talent were clearly defined. Youth with spiritual virtue is a concept applied to people who have reached maturity, are free-spirited, perfect, and fully enlightened. It means intellectual, spiritual, and moral maturity of a person, becoming a master of his chosen profession, forming as a person, burning his soul for the development of the Motherland, the well-being of the nation, and having the ability to be creative and creative with noble ideas and intentions. A person with spiritual virtue sets an example for others, and makes them follow him. The more such people there are, the more perfect the society will be, the more science and culture will develop. A great future is created and raised only when it relies on the young generation. reforms will bring the expected success if they feel involved in the changes taking place in our country and actively participate in their implementation. In other words, only spiritual youth can create a great future

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